

THE EFFECTIVE USE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS IN INDEPENDENT MASTERING OF MUSIC DISCIPLINES.

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Annotation: the future of each society is determined by the extent to which the educational system is developed, which is an integral part of it and a vital necessity. Today, the reform and improvement of the system of continuous education of our country, which is following the path of independent development, raising to a new level of quality, introducing advanced pedagogical and information technologies into it, and improving educational efficiency, has risen to the level of Public Policy. The world pedagogical experience confirms that the possibility of modern pedagogical technologies to interest students (or students) in the sciences, to increase their activity in independent work is unlimited.

Keywords: Music Culture, mobile phones, computers, PoverPoint software, independent work, pedagogical technologies, continuing education, music education.

The general pedagogical and didactic requirement for all stages of Education consists in improving the effectiveness of independent work on the basis of the student's (or student's) programming knowledge, imagination and skills, strengthening his interest in scientific thinking, educational science, deepening his professional knowledge, increasing their activity during theoretical and practical training.

The task of education today is to teach students to be able to operate independently in the conditions of an information and educational environment, which increases day by day, to use the information flow wisely. To do this, it is necessary to provide them with the opportunity and conditions for continuous independent work.

Interest in the application of innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process, attention is gaining momentum day by day. One of the reasons for this to happen is that, until then, in traditional education, students - students are set to acquire only their ready-made knowledge, while modern technologies teach them to search for the knowledge they are acquiring, study and analyze independently, and even draw conclusions themselves.

According to teachers, researchers, practitioners studying issues, problems of pedagogical technologies, pedagogical technology is defined as improving educational efficiency, computer, distance learning, or the use of various techniques that are only related to Information Technology and that need to be applied in the teaching process.

The most basic foundation of pedagogical technology - we believe that this depends on the technologies chosen by the teacher and the student to achieve cooperation as a guaranteed result from the established goal, that is, if each educational technology used in the teaching process, achieving a guaranteed result on the goal, can organize collaborative activities between the teacher and the student, achieve a positive result, students in the learning process can think independently, work creatively, , and this is the basis of the

teaching process, when the teacher is able to create opportunities and conditions for their activities.

Researchers argue that the quality of data acquisition depends on the level of information perception and activity of the learners, while learning involves 10% of people reading, 20% listening, 30% seeing, and 90% self-fulfilling. It is on the basis of pedagogical technologies that creates a favorable environment for the independent implementation of the tasks and tasks given by the students themselves. Even in musical education today, modern pedagogical technologies are used most efficiently. Because pedagogical technologies allow students to independently play and sing and analyze songs on an instrument, increase musical literacy, sing in pure intonation, strengthen memory, form a figurative image, be able to fully show their abilities, acquire thorough knowledge of music Sciences, expand the scope of reflection and conversation, free and creative thinking, find a decision to cooperate between a teacher and a group, ensures the achievement of a number of important educational goals, such as achieving the priority of democratic and humanitarian ideas in the pedagogical process.

Continuing education creates the necessary conditions for the formation of a creative, socially active, spiritually rich personality and the preparation of highly qualified competitive personnel. The main goal of music education and education is to form in students the skills of studying the art of music on the basis of beauty laws and to compose the culture of modern music in them. Therefore, this goal sets a number of tasks for the teacher to create an understanding in students of musical – artistic taste and moral aesthetic feelings: the development of their creative abilities, interest in the art of music and their artistic need in musical activities, the formation of a culture of music literacy, the expression of music – era, life, human emotions and his dreams.

Musical subjects at school ensure that the child is healthy, comprehensively matured and formed, in which he awakens the feeling of striving for study, prepares him for regular education.

To develop musical education, it will be necessary to do the following:

- priority training of qualified educational and pedagogical personnel;
- search and introduction of effective psychological and pedagogical methods of musical education;
- organizational, psychological, pedagogical and methodological support of raising children in the family;
- creation of modern educational and methodological manuals, technical means, toys and games and their production;
- to create conditions for the spiritual and moral education of children on the basis of the rich cultural and historical heritage of the people and universal values.

Without mobile phones, computers, many other modern electronic means of communication, everyday life in today's turbulent period is absolutely unimaginable. Consequently, innovations in communication are also widely applied to its traditional types, such as plain phones and Postal Service.

In fact, modern means and technology of communication with their capabilities are becoming one of the main quality indicators of our time. We do not have a day when we have not heard or read about the famous brands of manufacturers of current communication techniques or online services that have become popular. However, only a modern mobile phone, tablet or computer itself is scarce to use them all. After all, not a single such equipment will work if

there is no cellular network signal or internet access. Therefore, in order to meet the needs of consumers, it is necessary first of all to expand and modernize the corresponding infrastructure.

Today, it remains one of the main directions for the development of the information and communication sector in our country. During the years of independence, great work was done to improve the reliability and quality of existing telecommunications services and to bring to life new types that meet the requirements of the Times. On the scale of the whole Republic, advanced switching equipment was installed and put into Operation, Fast Optis fiber communication lines were laid. Such changes in the network have a clear strategy. After all, the industry is gaining momentum.

Information and communication tools in particular are very helpful in teaching music subjects. The subject "history of music" can be used to draw effective information from Internet sites in providing more accurate coverage of the life and work of composers to readers. The presentation of a collection of art films, documentaries, created to devote to their life and work during the lesson will give an effective result in students' deep mastery of the topic. Presentation awareness through the PowerPoint program from information obtained from the internet also ensures a meaningful course of the lesson.

The great dargah of World Music Culture was founded by the Austrian V.A.Mosart, German composer L.V.Beethoven, Italian composers J.Rossini, J.Verdi, Russian composers M.P.Mussorgsky, P.I.Tchaikovsky, N.A.Popular music artists such as Rimsky-Korsakov believe that listening to musical masterpieces, as well as samples of our traditional classical national music using gram recording during the lesson will help students to form and grow their musical listening activity and memory.

The main requirements for improving the effectiveness of pedagogical technology processes and ensuring the physical development of those involved are met in the process of properly organized training.

If the process of "application of pedagogical technologies "of classes" music culture" is formed at the required level, the effectiveness of the formation of musical taste and physical fitness in students increases. Through this process, the deep absorption of our national musical wealth, classical singing, into the minds of the next generation is realized.

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